

Operational Equipments for Wind and Waves Monitoring in Offshore Marine Industry

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Abstract—This paper present specific systems for monitoring winds and waves in offshore area, installed at the Galata platform, Bulgaria. The novelty of using this equipment consists in: 1. obtaining much more precise information on several adjustable height levels; 2. reducing costs and problems during installation on a fixed offshore platform; 3. the much more efficient design of the wind turbine using the database provided by these equipments. The wind monitoring device WindCube is located on the top level of the platform. The waves monitoring device from Aanderaa was install on the underwater platform structures. The data collected will be useful for obtaining the metocean data necessary for sizing the resistance elements of a wind turbine, but also for estimating the wind potential.

Keywords— monitoring systems, Black Sea, WindCube, ADCP, Aanderaa, Vaisala, metocean data

I. INTRODUCTION

The operational purpose in monitoring meteorological parameters (wind, wave, current, wind-wave intersections) is focused on the end user. The beneficiaries of this stored data are government services, coastal industrial units and research institutes. The direct users of this data are coastal zone administrators, maritime transport units, offshore industry representatives, ports, fishing organizations, tourism and recreation industry representatives. Several collection systems have been installed in the Black Sea, but not all of them are functional from the point of view of collecting and transmitting marine data. These systems are installed both in the onshore and offshore areas [1].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGIES

A. Systems for monitoring winds and waves in the offshore area

Obtaining the most accurate data in the case of the installation of a floating wind turbine in the offshore area (FOWT) must be based, apart from satellite data, on data actually measured in situ. For wind, it can use classic

anemometers with cups and vanes (wind vanes) that give the value at the measurement point [1], [2]. In the present work, a high-performance Vaisala Lidar WindCube device is used [3]. For waves and currents, a SeaGuard II Doppler Current Profiler device is used (Aanderaa)[4].

To monitor the parameters of waves and surface currents, a SeaGuard II Aanderaa device was used, fixed with the help of two divers on the structures of the Galata platform, Bulgaria (35 km offshore S-E of Varna, Latitude 43.04456° / Longitude 28.19323°) under water (Fig.1a), attached to one leg of the platform seems easy solution, good quality data for currents.

A Vaisala Lidar WindCube device was used to monitor the wind, which improves the accuracy of the wind speed (Fig. 1b)[3].

Fig.1. Systems for monitoring : a) waves- SeaGuard II Aanderaa device

b)

Fig.1. Systems for monitoring : b) wind-WindCube Vaisala device

For an efficient operation and maintenance of the floating wind turbine, it is also necessary to evaluate the parameters of waves and surface currents. The optimization of the basic structure of the floating wind turbine is done taking into account the in-situ measurements of the velocity fields at different heights in the location area.

The methodology used is *the wind speed field reconstruction*.

“Wind Field Reconstruction is a class of algorithms used to convert raw line-of-sight (LOS) Lidar data into 10-minute average Cartesian wind components: horizontal wind speed, wind direction, vertical wind speed, and turbulence intensity. Generally, they include geometric translations, and averaging.”[5]

The operating principle of the equipment is (LOS-lines-of-sight), based on 5 laser beams, oriented towards the cardinal points [3]. A new one wind speed is generated by scalar averaging per second, used last four lines of sight (LOS) The aim is to finally obtain a reconstruction of the wind speed field, eliminating the risks of in-situ measurement uncertainties.

B. Data

Using these equipment, the collection of data at the Galata platform is pursued for a period of 16 months, starting with the 2nd month after installation. The equipment will then be moved to the offshore area in Romania, to a platform where data replication is being pursued.

The input data are: site topography (based on GPS input), wind data (wind speed and wind direction at several heights at a single location), waves and currents raw data.

The use of a Vaisala Lidar WindCube device allows obtaining much more precise informations on several adjustable height levels, up to 250 ... 300 m high. This covers the entire area of the wind turbine rotor.

The use of this offshore equipment mounted on a fixed platform is a novelty, because its installation involves high costs and major installation (deployment) problems (power source and permanent connection to the Internet).

The wind data coming from WindCube offshore is automatically transmitted to the manufacturer's website (Vaisala insightfully) every hour.

The device is programmed to measure at 12 specific heights between 40 ... 250 m required by the system designer. These raw data can also be retrieved manually from

the internal hard disk. With these data and using other (historical) satellite data existing in the databases, the maximum predictable wind value for a period of 10 or 100 years is obtained.

For the SeaGuard II Doppler Current Profiler (Aanderaa) wave and current equipment:

The data (row data) can be downloaded from the internal SD Card or can be retrieved from the shore and processed using the AADY Real-Time Collector software.

Row data of type **.bin** are input data for the Aanderaa DataStudio 3D software which provides tabular data and histograms regarding parameter values (height, temperature, mean direction, peak period) every 30 minutes (Fig.2, Fig.3, Fig.4).

Fig.2. Signifiant height and temperature

Fig.3. Signifiant wave height

Fig.4. Wave mean direction, wave peak period, significant height

At this time, the Aanderaa DCP SeaGuard II underwater system was found by our diver broken and bent; it is possible that this is due to tug maneuvering near Galata or waves action.

So, the reinforced system was prepared at Constanta Maritime University for repositioning at next travel on Galata platform. The diver managed to repositioning the system and fix the device. New tilt is now 8.57° (Fig.5)[6].

Fig.5. The new position of the Aanderaa DCP Seaward II

At Aanderaa device, the GSM modem connection system was replaced with a more secure one: a mini PC connected by cable to the GALATA router (to avoid the wireless system) (Fig. 6). The purpose is to make the connection with the underwater device and to manage the connection and control from shore and to recover the data from the internal SD card [6], [7], [8].

Also, these data, like the wind data, are supplemented with satellite and historical data. By combining the wind and wave data, it is possible to estimate the maximum value and the probability that the winds, waves and currents will have the same direction and the maximum value at the same moment for a time period of 10 years and 100 years [9].

Fig.6. The connection Galata router-cable-mini PC

The turbine and its floating base are dimensioned for this maximum value obtained, and for the estimated lifetime of the turbine of 25 years [10], [11],[12].

For the profiler wave and current system, the advantages are the same (data regarding the wave direction and the value and direction of the speed on several adjustable depth levels)[9], [12].

The value of this equipment justifies the precision and complexity of the data obtained. The technical problems regarding the mounting of the equipment attached to the platform leg so that the presence of the platform leg does not affect the accuracy of the measurements; the problems related to the installation of the connecting cables, as well as the connection to the shore so that we get total control of the equipment, so as to avoid data loss, are a separate topic that will be presented in another paper [8], [11].

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Local geographical analysis is one of the important tasks in the design of wind floating offshore turbines. Also the evaluation of waves' parameters and of surface currents, as well as local measurements of the velocity fields at various heights of the land in the studied location.

The results obtained with equipment are:

Lidar WindCube

- for the given location, *wind reconstruction distribution*; that means, the distribution of radial wind speeds along the axis, with the deviations on the components;
- *average of measurements every 10 minutes*; this means the distribution of average speeds and direction of the high-frequency wind every 10 minutes. At each measurement, the device validates the speed with a signal, and the validated values contribute to the calculation of the average speed.

- *reanalysis of the flow of speeds*, taking into consideration the deviations of the radial speeds. The final values are compared with the statistical databases [9] and it is possible to estimate what the main wind speed is in a radius of 100 m around the Galata location.

Both datasets are stored in the system, whereas only corrected data are sent to Wind web.

The Aanderaa DCP SeaGuard II underwater system acoustically measures wave characteristics. The parameters of the currents and waves are measured on height levels, the average values are calculated and compared with the statistical databases, after which they are selected/filtered for

periods of the order of minutes or tens of minutes and transmitted to the PC. The final values are validated according to the registered differences.

The results obtained during maintenance:

Lidar WindCube

- near the Galata platform, the Saturn platform from Petroleum Services Group (GSP), was anchored, which from December 2023 started drilling works. After the completion of the drilling, this drilling platform remained in position, attached to Galata, and remain in the position till now. The drilling activity was carried out incorrectly and the entire Galata platform was covered with drill mud, which dried on the walls. One of the Windcube beam hit the Saturn platform. In the Fig. 7, camera is mounted on the WindCube horizontal surface.

Fig.7. The WindCube works with 3 beams out of 4

The dust and mud from drilling affected the wiper system, the washing liquid in the 60 l tank was found empty, because of continuous washing.

The rubber blade worked without water, which led to its destruction (Fig.8).

Fig.8. The device's wiper is destroyed

It is necessary to monitor the liquid level in the tank and to top it up with distilled water.

The Aanderaa DCP SeaGuard II underwater system

- was found by the diver broken and bent; it is possible that this is due to tug maneuvering near Galata or waves action. So, the reinforced system was prepared at Constanta for repositioning it (Fig. 9).

Fig.9. The positioning system destroyed

- At Aanderaa DCP SeaGuard II, the GSM modem connection system was replaced with a more secure one: a mini PC connected by cable (30m of CAT6 network cable was mounted by CMU [6]) to the GALATA router (to avoid the wireless system).

In conclusion:

- Using a Lidar WindCube type device allows obtaining much more precise information about the wind on several adjustable height levels, up to 250 ..300 m high

- The use of this offshore equipment mounted on a fixed platform is a novelty, because its installation involves high costs and major installation problems (strong power source and permanent connection to the Internet).

- For the wave and current profiler system, Aanderaa DCP SeaGuard II, the advantages are the same. The value of this equipment justifies the precision and complexity of the data obtained.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V., Akhipkin, Feodor, Gippius, K.P., Kolterman, G., Surkova, “ Wind waves in the Black Sea : results of hindacast study”, Natural hazards and Earth System Science, 14 (11), (2014).
- [2] Rusu, E., (2023). An evaluation of the expected wind dynamics in the Black Sea in the context of the climate change” in Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy, vol. 4 (2023)
- [3] <https://www.vaisala.com/en/products/wind-energy-windcube>. Accessed March 31, 2024
- [4] <https://www.aanderaa.com/profiling-current-meter>. Accessed May 27, 2024
- [5] https://www.vaisala.com/sites/default/files/documents/2022_WindEuropeEC_Hybrid_wind_reconstruction_poster.pdf
- [6] <https://cmu-edu.eu/proiect-blow/>
- [7] <https://blow-project.eu/>
- [8] M., Silion, G., Suci, L., Luminariu, C., Beceanu, C., Alexandru, S., Stefanescu, M.L., Rosu, I., Taranu, F.V. Panaitescu, M., Panaitescu, I., Voicu, A.A., Scupi, L.C., Stan, G., Raicu, L., Necula, “ Complex system for monitoring environmental factors at the Galata platform in the Black Sea”, ECAI, June 27-28, 2024, Iasi, Romania (will be published).
- [9] Valorem d’Energie, “ BLOW preliminary Meteocean data report”, D3.1.1, France, 2023.
- [10] X., Li, Q., Xiao, E., Wang, C., Peyrard, R.T., Gonçalves, “The dynamic response of floating offshore wind turbine platform in wave-current condition”, 2023.
- [11] H., Li, CG., Huang, C., Guedes Soares, “A real-time inspection and opportunistic maintenance strategies for floating offshore wind turbines”, in Ocean Engineering, vol. 256, 2022.
- [12] F.V., Panaitescu, M., Panaitescu, C., Panait, A.A.Scupi, L., Stan, C., Fatar, G., Suci, M., Silion, S., Stefanescu, N., Capbun, N., Zlatev, “Meteocean specifications for wind data base on the Black Sea”, in Journal of Marine Technology and Environment, vol. 2, Nautica Publish house Constanta, Romania, 2023, pp 58-64.